

Attention-Enhanced Support Vector Classification for Early Chronic Kidney Disease Prediction

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Abstract

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a major noncommunicable disease characterized by gradual kidney function decline and limited early-stage symptoms, making timely diagnosis challenging yet critically important. In many developing healthcare systems, delayed detection leads to increased morbidity, mortality, and significant financial burden due to expensive renal replacement therapies. Although machine learning models have shown promising performance in CKD prediction, many traditional approaches rely on static or correlation-based feature selection methods that may overlook complex interactions among clinical variables. This study proposes an Attention-Enhanced Support Vector Classification framework for early CKD prediction using longitudinal patient health data collected between 2018 and 2023, comprising 2,859 records and 87 clinical attributes. The proposed approach integrates an attention mechanism to dynamically assign importance weights to features before classification using a Support Vector Classifier (SVC), enabling adaptive learning of the most predictive clinical indicators. After data preprocessing, encoding, normalization, and model training, the baseline SVC achieved an accuracy of 95.7%. The attention-enhanced model improved performance to 98.3% accuracy, with notable gains in precision, recall, and F1-score, particularly for the minority CKD class, demonstrating improved handling of class imbalance. Additionally, the attention mechanism enhances interpretability by identifying influential features, supporting transparent and clinically meaningful decision-making. The results indicate that combining attention-based feature weighting with SVC offers a robust, accurate, and interpretable solution for early CKD detection, with strong potential for integration into clinical decision support systems in low-resource healthcare environments.

Keywords: *Chronic Kidney Disease, Support Vector Classifier, Attention Mechanism, Feature Selection, Machine Learning*